

DYNAMIC DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF POLYMERIC MATERIALS USING ALUMINUM SHPB TECHNIQUE AND PULSE SHAPER

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SUMMARY: The Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar(SHPB) technique with a special experimental apparatus can be used to obtain the material behaviors under high strain rate loading condition. Attempts to apply the Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar in measurement on polymeric materials suffer from limitations on the maximum achievable strain and from high noise to signal ratios. This paper introduces a Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar technique, which overcomes these limitations. The proposed method uses aluminum pressure bars to achieve a closer impedance match between the pressure bars and the specimen materials, thus providing both a low noise to signal ratio data and a longer input pulse for higher maximum strain. In addition, a pulse shaper technique was used for increasing the rise time of the incident pulse to ensure stress equilibrium and homogeneous deformation in the specimen under dynamic compression. The details of dynamic stress equilibrium with varying pulse shapers on the specimen surfaces are investigated. The dynamic deformation behaviors of Polymeric material under compressive high strain rate are evaluated using the modified SHPB technique.

KEYWORDS: SHPB(Split Hopkinson Pressure Bar), Dynamic Deformation, High Strain Rate, Pulse shaper, Polycarbonate, Aluminum.

INTRODUCTION

The high strain rate stress-strain responses of polymers and polymeric composite materials have received increased scientific and industrial attention in recent years. Polymeric materials are subjected to dynamic loading and high strain rate deformation in a variety of important applications such as aircraft and automotive components, as well as during high speed processes such as extrusion and blow molding. The features of polymeric materials are low strength, low wave propagation velocity and low mechanical impedance. In order to obtain the material characteristics for polymeric materials, we need to have a thorough understanding of the dynamic mechanical response and energy dissipation under high strain rate loading in detail. However, it is not easy to get accurate mechanical properties under the high strain rate loading condition.

The conventional split Hopkinson pressure bar(SHPB) is a most widely used method for investigating the dynamic behavior of high strength materials in the range of strain rate of $10^2/s \sim 10^4/s$ [1]. The SHPB technique has been continually modified to determine the dynamic properties of a variety of engineering materials such as metals, concrete, ceramic and polymeric and rubbers [2,3,4]. Especially for the polymers and polymeric composite materials

whose mechanical impedance and the wave propagation velocity are extremely low and slow, respectively, compared to conventional bar material such as steels, serious experimental problems occur. These problems include unacceptably high noise ratios to signal and the mismatch between soft material specimen and steel pressure bar. Also, to obtain valid experimental results on soft specimens in the SHPB technique, the specimen must deform uniformly under dynamic stresses equilibrium state. Furthermore, the specimen must deform at a nearly constant strain rate, which does not allow significant variation in strain rates during one experiment.

In this paper, we modified the conventional SHPB technique to obtain more accurate dynamic compressive stress strain data for polycarbonate. The modified techniques use an aluminum SHPB bar set-up and the pulse shaper technique to achieve constant strain rates in the polycarbonate specimen during a SHPB experiment. In addition, a modified SHPB technique has been used to determine the dynamic material properties of polycarbonate under the impact compressive loading conditions with various strain rates.

THEORY OF CONVENTIONAL SHPB TECHNIQUE

The SHPB technique consists of a striker bar, an incident bar, a transmitted bar, and a specimen placed between the incident and transmitted bars. An air gun launches the striker bar to impact at the incident bar, and that impact causes an elastic compressive wave generated at the impact face. The elastic compressive wave travels in the incident bar toward the specimen. The striker bar is unloaded from the incident bar when the elastic compressive wave travels through the striker bar reflects at the free surface as a tensile wave and returns to the impact face. Once the elastic compressive wave reaches the specimen a part of the incident pulse reflects from the bar-specimen interface because of the material impedance mismatch, and part of it transmits through the specimen. The transmitted pulse emitted from the specimen travels along the transmitted bar until it hits the end of the bar. A strain gage mounted on the incident bar measures the incident pulse (ε_i) and reflected pulse (ε_r), and a strain gage mounted on the transmitted bar measures the transmitted pulse (ε_t).

The conventional analysis is based on the mechanics of the elastic wave propagation in bars. According to the theory of elastic wave propagation, the stress and the particle velocity of a single wave can be accurately determine from the associated strain measured by strain gages. Furthermore, it is assumed that those quantities are not only known at the measuring points but everywhere in the bar because an elastic wave can be shifted to any distance knowing the wave propagation theory. Thus, the transmitted pulse can be shifted to the transmitted bar specimen interface to obtain the output force and velocity can be determined via the incident and reflected pulse shifted to the input bar specimen interfaces. When the waves are known at bar specimen interfaces, associated stress and particle velocities can be added. The forces at both faces of the specimen are then given by the following equations [5].

$$F_1 = EA(\varepsilon_i + \varepsilon_r) \quad (1)$$

$$F_2 = EA\varepsilon_t \quad (2)$$

The subscription 1 and 2 are used in this description to denote the incident and transmitted bar ends of the specimen, respectively. Where A is the cross sectional area of the pressure bar, and E is the Young's modulus of the bar material.

It is assumed that the specimen deforms uniformly. If these assumptions are valid, a simplification can be made equating the force on each side of the specimen (i.e., $F_1 = F_2$). Equating Eqn. 1 and Eqn. 2, we obtain $\varepsilon_t = \varepsilon_i + \varepsilon_r$.

The stress is calculated from the force divided by the specimen original area, A_s . The stress, strain, and strain rate in the specimen can be obtained as follows.

$$\sigma_{specimen} = E \frac{A}{A_s} \varepsilon_t \quad (3)$$

$$\varepsilon_{specimen} = -2 \frac{C_0}{L} \int \varepsilon_r dt \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{specimen} = -2 \frac{C_0}{L} \varepsilon_r(t) \quad (5)$$

Where, L is the initial length of the specimen and C_0 is wave propagation velocity. The foregoing calculations are based on the assumptions that the specimen undergoes homogeneous deformation and that the elastic bars are made of the same material with the same cross sectional area.

A fundamental difference between a high strain rate test and a quasi-static test is that the effects of inertia and wave propagation become more important at higher strain rates. Even when the specimen has been evaluated to be deforming uniformly, longitudinal and radial inertia caused by the rapid particle accelerations imposed during high strain rate testing can influence the measured stress strain behaviors. The errors due to both longitudinal and radial inertia have been analysed, and corrections have been derived for these error. This analysis gives that

$$\sigma(t) = \sigma_m(t) + \rho_s \left(\frac{L_s^2}{6} - \nu_s \frac{D^2}{8} \right) \frac{\delta^2 \varepsilon(t)}{\delta t^2} \quad (6)$$

Where σ_m is the measured stress, ρ_s is the density of the specimen, ν_s is the Poisson's ratio, L_s is the specimen length, and D is the specimen diameter. This expression predicts that errors are minimized if the strain rate is held constant or if the term inside the brackets is set to zero by choosing specimen dimensions such that

$$\frac{L_s}{D} = \sqrt{\frac{3\nu_s}{4}} \quad (7)$$

From Eqn. 6, L/D ratio of the specimen should be chosen by Eqn. 7 to remove inertia effect in the specimen. In this paper, we chose cylindrical specimen has a length of 5 mm and a diameter of 10 mm.

MODIFIED SHPB TECHNIQUE

The conventional SHPB technique is the most widely used method for investigating the dynamic behavior of varying engineering materials. However, the direct application of this technique for testing low strength and low impedance materials has serious problems. Table 1

summarizes the density, Young's modulus, wave propagation velocity and mechanical impedance values for a range of typical pressure bar and polycarbonate specimen materials.

Table 1: Comparison of mechanical properties between bar as specimen materials in SHPB experimental

Properties Materials	Density ρ (kg/m ³)	Elastic modulus E (GPa)	Wave speed C_0 (m/s)	Impedance Z (10 ⁶ kg/m ² ·s)	$Z_{\text{Specimen}}/Z_{\text{bar}}$ (%)
STB-2	7700	225	5160	39.7	3.7
PEEK-1000	1320	4.4	1825	2.4	62.5
Al-7075	2810	71.7	5051	14.2	10.5
Polycarbonate	1150	1.9	1285	1.5	100

Fig. 1 shows typical incident, reflected and transmitted strain signals for the polycarbonate specimen by a SHPB technique with different bar materials. The stress wave signals are obtained from strain gages attached on incident and transmitted bars, respectively. The first in the solid line is the incident pulse. And, the second with the symbols on line is the reflected pulse. If the impedance of the specimen is less than pressure bar, the two pulse are always opposite in sign. The symbol on line is the transmitted pulse. The result out of the big impedance mismatch between the pressure bar and specimen is shown in Fig. 1-(a). The low mechanical impedance of the specimen allows the interface to move almost freely under stress wave loading because most of the incident pulse is reflected backward into the incident bar. Only a small portion of the loading pulse is transmitted through the specimen into the transmitted bar, so the transmitted strain signal has a very small amplitude as we can see in Fig. 1-(a). It is noted that the mechanical impedance of the polycarbonate is only 3.7 percent of the mechanical impedance of the STB-2 steel pressure bar as shown in Table 1.

Fig. 1: Voltage vs. time obtained by using a various pressure bar in polycarbonate specimen (a) using the STB-2 pressure bar (b) using the PEEK-100 pressure bar

Realizing the low impedance of many structural polymers, such as polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) and polycarbonate (PC), a number of researchers have explored the benefits of using polymers for the pressure bars in an SHPB to test low mechanical impedance material. However, when the polycarbonate is tested with a PEEK-1000 pressure bar, the mechanical impedances of specimen and pressure bar material are similar as shown in Table 1. Fig. 1-(b) shows most of the incident pulse is transmitted forward into the transmitted bar. It is noted

that the difference of impedances between pressure bar and specimen too much or too small interrupts interpretation of the measurement.

An aluminum pressure bar set-up for the SHPB to test polycarbonate has been used in this paper. Al 7075-T6511 pressure bars offer to overcome the difficulties associated with the bar and specimen impedance mismatch.

The bar length has to be twice of wavelength of stress pulse in the bars to have one dimensional stress wave in the bars and specimen, so the ratio of the length to the diameter of the bars was designed to be 100. Two bars are made of the same material of striker bar and have the identical diameter with striker bar. In this study, the incident, transmitted and striker bars are made of Aluminum 7075-T6511 whose yield strength is 503MPa, the modulus of elasticity is 71.7GPa and the density is 2.81g/cm³. Al 7075-T6511 pressure bars had a common diameter of 16mm. The length of the incident, transmitted, and striker bars were 1,600, 1,500 and 300mm, respectively.

The pulse shaper material was chosen so that the pulse shaper deformed plastically in a designed manner upon impact, which effectively controlled the shape of the incident pulse in the incident bar. The gradually increasing pulse shaper area upon impact by the striker bar allows more momentum to transfer from the striker to the incident bar, which significantly increases the rising time of the incident pulse. The proper choice of the pulse shaper material and dimensions control the profile of the incident pulse. We used copper(Cu-11000) pulse shaper of a length of 5 mm and a diameter of 10 mm. Fig. 1 shows the schematic of the modified aluminum SHPB apparatus with a pulse shaper.

Fig. 2: Schematic of the modified aluminum SHPB apparatus with pulse shaper for testing the polycarbonate

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

An aluminum SHPB with a pulse shaper was employed to determine the dynamic deformation behavior of polycarbonate. Fig. 3 shows typical incident, reflected and transmitted strain signals from an experimental for a polycarbonate specimen using a SHPB without a pulse shaper and with a Cu-11000 pulse shaper.

Fig. 3: Voltage vs. time obtained by strain gages in polycarbonate using the Al7075-T6511 pressure bar (a) without pulse shaper (b) with pulse shaper

The shape of the incident pulse in Fig. 3-(a) shows the significant fluctuation and drastic rising time. It is found from Fig. 3-(a) that the drastic rising time of the incident pulse is $14.5\mu\text{s}$. And, it is shown that the fluctuation and oscillation at the initial portion of the top duration are changed significantly. It is recognized from comparing Fig. 3 -(a) with Fig. 3-(b) that the rising time and top duration have been changed. The shape of incident pulse is significantly modulated. It is found that the rising time and top duration in Fig. 3-(b) become longer and flatter than these of Fig. 3-(a). The rising time of the incident pulse increased to $37.3\mu\text{s}$ with pulse shaper as shown in Fig. 3-(b). It is noted that the rising time of the incident pulse can be increased about 157% by using a pulse shaper. And, it is found from the Fig. 3-(b) that the fluctuation and oscillation by using a pulse shaper are decreased and smooth.

The dynamic stress equilibrium in a specimen during the testing in an SHPB can be assessed by comparing the 1-wave and 2-wave (or 3-wave) stress strain response of the specimen. The 1-wave analysis represents the conditions at the specimen transmitted bar interface and is referred to as the specimen “back end stress”. In a 2-wave analysis, the sum of the incident and reflected pulse forms is proportional to the specimen “front end stress” and represents the conditions at the incident bar specimen interface.

Fig. 4: Dynamic strain rate curve and comparison between the front end stress and the back end stress, respectively: (a) No pulse shaper; (b) pulse shaper

Figure 4 shows the strain rate and the stress histories on the end face (front end and back end) of polycarbonate specimen with and without pulse shaper. Fig. 4-(a) shows a large difference between the front end stress and back end stress in early deformation period. And, the front end stress of Fig. 4-(a) shows significant stress fluctuations. The difference between the front end stress and back end stress involved non-uniform strain rate. Fig. 4-(b) shows that the stress state is uniform throughout the specimen and the front end stress equally oscillates above and below of the back end stress. Fig. 4 indicates that the specimen has been deformed in dynamic equilibrium over nearly the entire duration of the experimental. The strain rate histories shown in Fig. 4-(a) indicated that strain rate was maintained at the same value for most of the test. When the striker bar impacts the pulse shaper, compressive forces are gradually transferred from the pulse shaper to the incident bar. The pulse shaper homogeneously deforms and increases the loading capacity by increasing its cross section area. The increase of the load carry capacity of the pulse shaper causes longer rising time in incident pulse. The longer rising time in incident pulse offers sufficient time of removing the dispersion or attenuation component of the incident pulse.

Fig. 5: Dynamic strain rate curves and typical dynamic strain history of a polycarbonate specimen with pulse shaper

The dark region in Fig. 5 indicates the time duration while the strain rate was maintained at the same value during the SHPB testing. The strain rate becomes a constant at $30 \mu\text{s}$ through $113.4 \mu\text{s}$. Since the stress equilibrium in the specimen was also achieved within these time periods, the dynamic stress strain curve at the strain rate of $3,404\text{s}^{-1}$ which was calculated with Eqn. 3 and Eqn. 4 and shown in Fig. 5. An accurate measure of the specimen response has been done within the strain range of $4.5\% \sim 26.5\%$.

Figure 6 summarizes the dynamic stress strain curve at strain rates from $2,000/\text{s}$ to about $4100/\text{s}$ for the polycarbonate. In Fig. 6, the symbols on and around lines represent experimental data point, whereas the lines are curve-fitted from the data. The dynamic compressive stress strain curves in the polycarbonate consist of three regions. The first region; there exists an initial elastic linear region where the strain is less than 5% strain. The second region; an initial linear region followed by the curve which is again nearly linear with decreases curve slope. The decreases curve slope means that polycarbonate begins yielding, and starts plastic deformation. The again nearly linear means the plastic deformation continues. The third region; there exist a non-linear second stage working hardening. The

reason for the final drop of stress in Fig. 6, is not caused by specimen fracture, but by specimen unloading. Examination of the specimens after testing reveals that the polycarbonate specimens are still intact with significant residual strain.

Fig. 6: Dynamic compressive stress strain curves for polycarbonate at various strain rates : 1.initial linear elastic ; 2. yielding and plastic deformation ; 3. second stage work hardening

Figure 7 shows the initial part of the first region (the initial elastic region) of the polycarbonate dynamic compressive stress strain curves with various strain rates.

Fig. 7: The first region dynamic compressive stress strain curve and fitting line with various strain rates

The initial elastic region can be linear fit using the least square method. From the fitting line in Fig. 7, we determine that dynamic compressive elastic modulus and yielding stresses at the various strain rates. Fig. 7 indicated that the maximum stress of the initial elastic region(or yielding stress) is 127.85MPa with independence of the increasing the strain rate. The fitting

slope (or elastic modulus) increased from 2.16GPa to 2.19GPa, 2.63GPa and 2.81GPa as the strain rate is increased from $1,750\text{s}^{-1}$ to $2,250\text{ s}^{-1}$, $3,450\text{ s}^{-1}$ and $4,100\text{ s}^{-1}$, respectively. It is noted that yielding stress is constant but, yielding strain decreases with increasing the strain rate under high strain rate.

Figure 8 shows the second and third region of the polycarbonate dynamic compressive stress strain curves with various strain rates.

Fig. 8: the second region of the dynamic compressive stress strain curve and fitting line with various strain rates

The second region consists of the yielding region and plastic deformation region. The plastic deformation occurs within the stress range 144Mpa ~ 175.85Mpa. The stress in the plastic deformation region increases with increasing strain rate. The plastic deformation begins at about 7.5% strain. In case of the $1,750\text{ s}^{-1}$ and $2,100\text{ s}^{-1}$, the plastic deformation progressed until the occurrence of the unloading. But, for the strain rate of the $3,450\text{ s}^{-1}$ and $4,100\text{ s}^{-1}$, the second stage work hardening region appeared to present continuous for the strain rate of the plastic deformation. The second stage work hardening increased with increasing the strain rate. It is found that polycarbonates maintain its general deformation characteristic over the high strain rate.

CONCLUSION

In this paper, the dynamic deformation behavior of polycarbonate under compressive loading condition is estimated by using an aluminum SHPB technique with a pulse shaper. The following experimental results are obtained.

- 1) The pulse shaper offers an optimum incident pulse that make the experimental stress-strain data valid under high strain rate using the SHPB technique in polymer specimen.
- 2) The dynamic compressive stress strain curves in the polycarbonate consist of three regions: the first region ; an initial elastic linear region, the second region ; yielding and plastic deformation region and the third region ; non-linear second stage working hardening region.

- 3) The dynamic yielding stress is found to be constant with increasing the strain rate. But, other characteristic of the dynamic stress strain curve such as are increased with increasing the strain rate.
- 4) The dynamic deformation behaviors of a polycarbonate is found to be sensitive to the high strain rate.

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